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Empirical Analysis Of Health Expenditure On Political Economic Growth In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The paper was centered on the empirical analysis of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria. Health is a very important aspect of an individual's wellbeing, and since individuals make a nation, therefore, healthcare could be regarded as one of the necessary conditions to achieving a sustainable long term economic development. The general objective of the paper was to examine the impact of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria. The paper also raised three research questions and three research hypotheses respectively in relation to the specific objectives of the paper. The data for the study were secondary and were analysed using Descriptive Statistics, Unit Root Test, Co-integration Test, Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) methodology, Diagnostic Statistics and Stability Test. The results showed that entire explanatory variables of the estimation met their expected signs for the model also that health expenditure has a significant impact on growth of the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: Health expenditure, economic growth, development, healthcare

INTRODUCTION

The first wealth of a nation is its health. There is empirical evidence that the health of a nation significantly enhances its economic development, and vice versa (Atun & Fitzpatrick, 2005). Health is one of the most important factors that determine the quality of human capital, a necessary factor for economic growth. In line with the above, a consensus of opinion have been formed among researchers recognizing health as a public good, the demand and supply of which cannot be left at the mercy of invisible hands or profit maximizing individual as well as on considerations of utility maximizing conduct alone . Hence, the need for the government to play a major role in delivering good and qualitative healthcare services that is accessible and affordable for the teeming population (Olarinde & Bello, 2014). The recognition of the importance of the above led the World Health Organisation (WHO) to propose at the 2010 World Health Assembly, issues that will address financing of health, which will ensure qualitative and affordable healthcare services (Ataguba and Akazili, 2010). The pattern of health

financing is therefore closely and indivisibly linked to the quality of health outcomes (health status), capable of achieving the long term goal of enhancing nation's economic development (Riman, 2012).

Health is a very important aspect of an individual's wellbeing, and since individuals make a nation, therefore, healthcare could be regarded as one of the necessary conditions to achieving a sustainable long term economic development. Health can be defined to mean general physical condition i.e. condition of the body or mind especially in terms of the presence or absence of illness, injuries or impairments. The issue of health is a very sensitive one because it deals with not just humans but with human body. Without a good health condition it is almost impossible to carry out any economic activity and if at all there is any it will certainly not be efficient and so we really have to take this subject seriously (Oluwatoyin, Folasade & Fagbeminayi, 2015).

The way a country finances its health care system is a critical determinant for reaching universal health coverage. This is so because it determines whether the health services that are available are affordable to those that need them or not. In Nigeria, the health sector is financed through different sources and mechanisms. The difference in the proportionate contribution from these stated sources determines the extent to which such health sector will go in achieving successful health care financing system. Unfortunately, in Nigeria, achieving the correct blend of health care expenditure remains a challenge. This review draws on relevant literature to provide an overview and the state of health care expenditure in Nigeria, including policies in place to enhance national productivity (Olatubi, Oyediran, Adubi & Ogidan, 2018).

Funding healthcare expenditure in Nigeria is from a variety of sources which include government, private sector, international donor agencies and NGOs. This study focuses on government funding. Government has the bulk of healthcare expenditure in Nigeria, which comprises budgetary allocations from government at all levels (Federal, States and Local Government). However, a high unemployment rate, soaring prices and a particularly more difficult economic situation for the majority of the poor population has severe consequences on the health status of Nigerians (Eneji, Dickson & Bisong, 2013).

The health system, in most cases, is synonymous to publicly owned health facilities, with several important private and non-state actors being downplayed (WHO, 2007). The functional capacities of the health system in these settings have gradually weakened, having failed to recognize and maximize efforts of all organizations, institutions, structures and resources primarily devoted to improving health. The health workforce all persons involved in activities primarily devoted to enhancing health is an essential block of any functioning health system in any country, in the absence of which clinical and public health services cannot be delivered to the population (WHO, 2006). Health governance is the administrative umbrella of the health system primarily concerned with policymaker- or government-led steering and rule-making functions targeted at achieving national health policy objectives for effective delivery of health services and attainment of universal health coverage (WHO, 2014).

A health care financing system involves the means in which funds are generated, allocated, and utilized for health care. It has three basic functions of collecting revenues, pooling resources, and purchasing services. The commonly used mechanisms for implementing these functions include tax-based financing, out-of pocket payments, donor funding, and health insurance (social and private). These methods are not mutually exclusive. In fact, most health systems adopt a mixture of various methods. The success of the different health financing methods can be measured by the overall effect on equity of access and health outcomes, revenue generation and efficiency, and the effects on user behavior and provider (Oлакunde, 2019).

In recent years impact of human capital formation, especially health status is realized to be an important predictor of economic growth not only in individual countries but across countries and over time. Consequently, health and its likely impact on individual's well-being and on economic growth have received immense importance at various levels (Edeme, Emecheta & Omej, 2017). The availability of healthcare services and the physical, biological, epidemiological and socio-economic environment in which a person lives, broadly determines the disease pattern, health status and generally the quality of life which reflects on the welfare of an individual. Implied is that if a country wants to develop successfully

economically, a fair amount of money should be spent on healthcare. Government intervention in undertaking fundamental role of allocation, distribution, stabilization and regulation has been encouraged in this regard, especially where or when market proves inefficient. In the case of Nigeria, despite of economic improvement, social and demographic indicators present a dismal picture. Nigeria still has one of the highest infant mortality rates and low life expectancy when compared with other developing countries. In addition, there is significant inequality in the distribution of financial and human resources in the health sector. Still, Nigeria's spending in the health sector is lower than 16 percent of GDP (UNDP 2013).

Economic growth and health expenditure in the Sub-Saharan Africa vary sub- significantly over time and across countries. Many studies in the health economics literature identify health expenditure as an important factor explaining differences in the level of economic growth, that is, economic development is to some extent attributed to better health outcomes which are partly a result of health expenditure. Adequate and efficient health related spending is widely considered as inevitable in the improvement of health status (Anyanwu & Erihijakpor, 2009). At the macro level, investment in health workforce and infrastructure is expected to improve health conditions, hence better human capital of the population and evidently more productivity (output). However, in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and other developing regions where resources are relatively scarce, health expenditure has received less attention in government budgets (Poullier, 2002). Africa's 10% contribution to the world's population relates to 3% of the world's health spending (WHO, 2010). Moreover, most of Sub-Saharan African countries still lag behind in terms of health care expenditure and outcomes due to a variety of reasons such as low household incomes, governments' allocations of insufficient shares of budgets to the health sector, mismanagement of resources allocated to the health sector, poor health care systems, among other things.

Nevertheless, health expenditure is considered very low. Funds voted for capital health goods in recent years have been massive, including ₦22.68 billion, ₦28.65 billion, ₦ 55.61 billion, and ₦71.11 billion in 2015-2018 (respectively). About ₦100 million was penciled to purchase kitchen utensils and food in the 2017 budget, and ₦850 million of the ₦42 billion State House budget was voted for cooking utensils (Abasifreke, Simeon & Bariika, 2022). Dr. Ehanire of the Ministry of Health, said Nigerians spend USD 1 billion per year seeking treatment outside Nigeria (Nan, 2016). Low health spending signals that the Nigerian government sees the sector as unworthy of its investment, and a strain on lean resources. This raises concerns like whether capital health spending can support economic development; whether a link can be fostered between recurrent health spending and development in Nigeria; and whether population growth slows or quickens development in Nigeria (Abasifreke, Simeon & Bariika, 2022).

Oluwatoyin, Folasade and Fagbeminiyi (2015) on which the current study is hinged ended his research period in 2012 but the current study extended its scope to 2020, as well as introducing credit to private sector and total government expenditure as financial deepening and economic indicators to bridge the gap created by investigating the long-run impact of health expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020 using standard econometric methodology. In the light of this, the current study is subdivided into five sections including introduction as section one, section two deals with literature review while section three is the research methods, Section four and five deals with the analysis and discussion of results; conclusion and recommendations.

Statement of the Problem

Childhood immunization, maternal mortality, HIV/AIDS life-saving anti-retroviral drugs are regarded as some of the most effective public health interventions in modern history. However, recent statistics from the WHO regarding Nigeria's health status is disturbing; the average life expectancy at 54 years is below the global average, maternal mortality is 608 per 100,000 live births, twice as high as South Africa's 300 per 1,000 and almost 10 times Egypt's 66 per 1,000. Besides, only 3% of HIV-positive mothers receive anti-retroviral treatment (Eneji, Dickson & Bisong, 2013). According to Omeruan, Bamidele and Phillips (2009) the major challenges of Nigeria healthcare system have been largely due to the unplanned consequences of social policy. Consequently, health services in Nigeria have suffered from decades of neglect, endangering Nigeria health status and national productivity. The healthcare system management

is in three tiers; tertiary healthcare- provided by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN), mostly coordinated through the university teaching hospitals and federal medical centres.

The secondary healthcare provision is by the state governments which manage the General Hospitals. The third tier is the Local Government (774 LGAs) which focuses on primary healthcare services administered in the dispensaries. It is the primary healthcare that suffers the most neglect. Women, children, and especially the core poor die from avoidable health problems such as infectious diseases, malnutrition, polio, guinea worm, measles, complications at pregnancy and childbirth. Government's expenditure has not provided adequate health infrastructure, especially in the rural areas of primary health care. The health sector suffers from the dearth of qualified healthcare personnel and regulations, as Nigeria's promising doctors, pharmacists, nurses and other health professionals continue to leave Nigeria to apply their services more profitably in other countries. Nigerians are being denied quality healthcare services, especially those in the rural areas. Between 2005 and 2012, Nigeria's HDI value increased from 0.434 to 0.471, an average annual increase of about 1.2% (HDR, 2013).

However, health spending as a proportion of the federal government expenditures shrank from an average of 3.5% in the 1970s to less than 2% in the 1980s and 1990s (FMOH, 2004). Nigeria was ranked 187th among the 191 United Nations member states in 2000. That same year, Nigeria spent 4USD per capita on health, below WHO's minimum benchmark of 14USD per capita for developing countries (WHO, 2000). By 2002, total health expenditure was dismal figure of 4.7% (WDR, 2005). In 2012, total health expenditure as percentage of GDP stood at 5.3%, ranked 153 out of 187th countries and territories. High profile individuals, especially the political class, continue to fly abroad on regular basis for medical treatment, further widening the inequality in accessing healthcare services. Increase in government expenditure and growth in per capita output in Nigeria do not speak for increase in social welfare and health status in particular. Nigeria's fiscal scenario poses significant risks to sustainable development, given that oil boom has increased government's expenditure from historical experiences of the 1970s. However, the size of government's non-productive spending and corruption has always swollen deficit budget. This calls for serious concern by policy makers to check the growth of government wage bills. Political corruption is responsible for budgetary inflation in Nigeria.

Furthermore, other related studies ended their investigation in 2015 but the current study examines the impact of health expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria from 2000 – 2021 with a robust dynamic model based on the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), where the response from the Real Gross Domestic Product to the selected explanatory variables are examined. This approach is most appropriate to fill the gap identified by this study, since it facilitates the long run equilibrium and short run adjustment process.

Finally, national productivity and overall political economic growth of any nation is the function of the health of such a nation. The improvement and extension of healthcare delivery in Nigeria have been constrained by gaps in financing, its contribution is still marginally low whereas the extent of its impact on economic growth is undermined and the desired results have not been met. This is particularly worrisome as several questions have been raised on the situation and which, the study intends to answer within its scope and context. What is responsible for this marginal contribution and how can this be addressed, is the thrust of this study.

Objectives of the Study

The overall objective of this study is to examine the impact of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to examine:

- (a) The impact of domestic public health expenditure on real gross domestic product in Nigeria,
- (b) The relationship between domestic private health expenditure and real gross domestic product in Nigeria and
- (c) The effect of out-of-pocket expenditure on real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Research Questions

Arising from the statement of the problem, the following research questions were raised and considered:

- (a) Does domestic public health expenditure influence real gross domestic product in Nigeria?

- (b) Is there any relationship between domestic private health expenditure and the real gross domestic product in Nigeria?
- (c) What effect does Out-of-pocket expenditure have on real gross domestic product in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

- H₀₁: Domestic public health expenditure has no significant impact on real gross domestic product in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between domestic private health expenditure and real gross domestic product in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: out-of-pocket expenditure does not contribute significantly to real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Issues

The impact of health expenditure and economic growth appears to be a new phenomenon in Nigerian economic literature. According to Ojo and Ojo (2022) health is necessary for happiness, increased productivity, the potential for self-sustaining growth and development, and a critical component of economic growth and development. Health expenditure is defined as the mobilization of funds for health care services; it is the provision of funds and resources to the government's planned activities to maintain people's health (Oyefabi, Aliyu & Idris, 2014). Olayiwola and Olusanya (2021) posited that inadequate and sustainable health financing is important to the attainment of Sustainable growth and development.

Olayiwola, Oloruntuyi and Abiodun (2017) argued that a fair amount of budget is spent on health care for achieving economic growth and development given the United Nations (UN) accommodation that countries should spend at least 8-10% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on health sector and the 2001 Abuja Declaration of committing at least 15% of the annual budget to health sector by each African country, the Nigerian government has been increasing its expenditure on the health sector in order to meet these benchmarks. For example, the government increases its expenditure on health from N84.46 billion in 1981 to N134.12 billion in 1986. However, it fell to N41.31 billion in 1987 before rising to N575.30 billion in 1989. Total government expenditure on health increased to N40,621.42 billion in 2002, dropped to N33,267.98 billion in 2003, and then increased to N104,810.8 billion in 2010. Between 2011 and 2014, government health spending increased to N113,76.30 billion in 2011, N122,722.66 billion in 2012, N131,678.87 billion in 2013, and N140,635.10 billion in 2014. Health-care spending was N1, 190.71 billion in 2019, N132.78 billion in 2020, and N1, 477.77 billion in 2021 (Awogbemi, 2022). Expenditure on health has been increasing on yearly basis in Nigeria due to total public and private allocation to health sector.

World Development Indicators (2021) reported that both out-of-pocket and domestic private health expenditure contributed more to the current health expenditures in Nigeria. Out-of-pocket (OOP) health expenditure is defined as the imposition of user-charges at the point of consuming health care services. In Nigeria, out-of-pocket payments, also known as household health expenditures, accounted for more than 90% of the cost of accessing health care. Donor funding and public-private partnerships are examples of private sector health financing (PPP). The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Bank, and the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS are among the health donors (UNAIDS). These donors' contributions may take the form of loans and grants, commodities (drugs, medical equipment), technical expertise, training, and research funding, among other things. Government donations and concession loans (which include approximately 25% non-reimbursement components) are the major sources of external financing for the health sector in developing countries (Olayiwola, Oloruntuyi and Abiodun, 2017).

Olayiwola and Olusanya (2021) cited the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID); Agencies Francaise Development (AFD); United States Agency for International Development (USAID); Directorate-General for International Cooperation (DFIS); the Global Fund for Disease Control (GFDC); the Partnership for Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health (PMNCH); the Medicines for Malaria

Venture (MMV); and Societe Generale (SDC). However, one of the major challenges of private sector health care financing is the lack of global coordination among donor agencies and the duplication of donor agency financing efforts in providing health care aid to developing countries. In addition, Olayiwola, Oloruntuyi and Abiodun (2017) asserted that the pattern of health financing is linked to the provision of health services. There are various methods of financing health care available around the world, including Nigeria. These sources include tax-based public sector health financing, household out-of-pocket health expenditure, private sector donor funding), and health insurance. challenges of financing and WHO and Abuja Declarations on health care in Nigeria include, but are not limited to, inequitable distribution of available health care workers, failure to attract and retain qualified health care workforce, particularly in rural communities, low remuneration to doctors and nurses and brain drain.

Theoretical Literature

The Wagner's Theory on Government Activities

The study was anchored on the Wagner's law of the increasing state activity (Wagner, 1883). The Wagner's hypothesis deals with the growing relative importance of government activities. According to Wagner, 1883 cited in Oni (2014) there are three reasons to expect an expansion of the scope of public activity. First, as nations developed, there was an increase in the complexity of legal relations and communications, as well as greater urbanization and population density, and this forces government to produce the regulatory framework that would accompany the greater intricacy of economic agent relations. Second, as income levels rise, societies demand more education, entertainment, more equitable income distribution, and more public services in general. Finally, the technological needs of an industrialized society necessitate greater amounts of capital infrastructure than are available from the private sector, necessitating government intervention to fill the void. The law was based on the assumption that there is a long run propensity for the scope of government to increase with higher levels of economic growth and development.

Therefore, Wagner was of the view that a fundamental relationship activities and economic growth. The higher level of economic growth requires higher level of public expenditure. Keynesian school of thought believes that expenditure can contribute to economic growth positively (Kur et al., 2020). From the foregoing, Wagner's law of increasing extension of state activity is central to this study because increased government spending leads to increased investment, profitability, and employment due to the multiplier effect on aggregate demand. When spending increases in the health sector, the multiplier effect results in an increase in disposable income, which raises demand for better education, health care, and housing. As a result, improved health status would boost economic activity, leading to economic growth and development as healthy people become more productive.

Endogenous Growth Theory

Endogenous growth theories describe economic growth which is generated by factors within the production process such as economies of scale, increasing return or induced technological changes; as opposed to exogenous factors such as increase in population. The several endogenous growth models link public spending with the economy's long-term growth. Barro (1990, 1991) Levine and Renelt (1992) among others have examined the relationship between public spending and economic growth. Specifically, some researchers have investigated the link between sectoral public expenditure such as public health care expenditure and health outcomes. Among such studies are Ricci and Zachariad (2006), Sparrow, Pradhan and Kruse (2009). Ricci and Zachariad (2006), used data covering 72 countries from 1961 to 1995, in order to investigate the determinants of public health outcomes in a macroeconomic perspective, taking into cognisance households' choices concerning education, health related expenditure and saving. They found evidence for a dual role of education as a determinant of health outcomes. Sparrow et al (2009) on the other hand, using panel data set of 207 Indonesian districts over a 4-year period from 2001 to 2004, concluded that district-level public health spending is largely driven by central government transfers.

Most of the studies on Nigeria examined the impact of health expenditure or health status on economic growth. Such studies include Dauda (2004). Dauda (2004) analyzed the impact of healthcare spending on economic growth in Nigeria, by adopting the neo-classical growth model. She used the ordinary least square methods of estimation and found a positive relationship between health care expenditure and economic growth.

Filmer and Pritchett (1999) in their own work found that public spending and health outcome are tenuously related. According to them doubling public spending from 3 to 6 percent of GDP would improve child mortality by only 9 to 13 percent. Surveying the literature on the link between public expenditure and outcome Pritchett (1996), notes that all of the negative or ambivalent findings on the effect of public spending on outcomes could potentially be a reflection of differences in the efficacy of spending which could arise due to a variety of reasons including corruption and patronage. Besides, it is also noted that the link between public spending and outcomes could be broken is the displacement of private sector effort by public spending. This argument is eloquently made in Filmer *et al.* (2000) while commenting on the weak links that several studies have found between public spending on health and health status. Although in most of the studies where public spending is found to have low or negligible impact, it is argued that public provision could lead to a crowding out of private sector provision, they have failed to question the efficacy of public spending.

Empirical Literature

A number of scholars have also done extensive study on the effect of public health expenditure and their effect on health outcomes. A group of literature in recent years has tried to examine the link between public health expenditure and health outcomes especially as it affects under-five mortality, infant mortality and life expectancy at births. Available studies so far document a range of effects, from no impacts, to limited impacts, and to significant impacts on only specific interventions. For instance, Anyanwu and Erhijakpor (2007) carried out a study on health expenditures and health outcomes in Africa and provided econometric evidence linking African countries' per capita total as well as public health expenditures and per capita income to two health outcomes: infant mortality and under-five mortality using data from 47 African countries. Health expenditures were found to have significant effect on infant mortality and under-five mortality. The results imply that for African countries, total health expenditures (as well as the public component) are certainly important contributor to health outcomes. In addition, infant and under-five mortality were found to be positively related to health outcome for Sub-Saharan Africa. The reverse is true for North-Africa where ethno-linguistic fractionalization and HIV prevalence positively affect health outcome while higher numbers of physicians and female literacy reduce these health outcomes.

Boachie and Ramu (2015) examined the relationship between public health expenditure and health status in Ghana. In their study, they examined the impact of public health spending on health status for the period 1990-2002 employing standard OLS and Newey-White estimation technique. After controlling for real per capita income, literacy level and female participation in the labour market, the study found evidence that the declining infant mortality rate in Ghana is explained by public health spending among other factors. Thus, they concluded that public healthcare expenditure is associated with improvement in health status through reduction in infant mortality.

Leaning on the above, Ahmed and Hasan (2016) analyzed the impact of public health expenditure and governance on health outcomes in Malaysia using data from 1984-2009. Adopting an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) cointegration framework, the results based on the bounds testing procedure show that a stable, long-run relationship exists between health outcomes and income level, public health expenditure, corruption and government stability. The results also reveal that public health expenditure and corruption affect long and short-run health outcomes. To improve the quality of life in the country, the study emphasize on the importance of health program while reducing or eliminating the corruption rate in the country. Also, using panel data set of Indian states between 1983-84 and 2011-12, Barenberg, Basu and Soyly (2015) study the impact of public health expenditure on the infant mortality rate, after

controlling for other relevant explanatory co-variables like per capita income, female literacy, and urbanization. The study found that public expenditure on healthcare dampens infant mortality rate. The baseline specification shows that an increase in public health expenditure by 1% of state-level GDP leads to a decrease in the infant mortality rate by about 8%. The study also finds that female literacy and urbanization also reduce the infant mortality rate.

Akinci, Samer, Farrukh and Akhmedjonov (2015) examined the impact of healthcare expenditures on selected health outcomes for 19 countries in the Middle East and North Africa region. Using panel data for 1990-2010, the study estimated the impact of both government and private healthcare expenditures on infant, under-five and maternal mortality rates. The results show that after controlling for co-explanatory variables, government and private spending on healthcare significantly improve infant under-five, and maternal mortality in the region, though its impact is not significant. In specific terms, a percentage increase in per capita government expenditure reduces the infant mortality rate by 8.6-9.5%, under-five mortality by 10.3-12 %, under-five deaths and maternal mortality by 26.0-26.3%. In the same vein, a percentage increase in the log per capita private expenditures reduces the infant mortality rate by 7.2-8.1%, under-five mortality rate by 9.5-9.8% and the maternal mortality rate by 25.8-25.9%. Disease is an epidemic that reduces the health status, life span of individuals, thereby affecting their level of productivity in the economy.

Furthermore, Nixon and Umann (2006) reported that although health expenditure and the number of physicians have made significant contributions to improvements of health sector performance proxy by infant mortality, health care expenditure has made a relatively marginal contribution to the improvement in life expectancy in the countries over the period of the analysis covering 1980 to 1995.

Olayinka and Olanrewaju (2013) analysed health expenditure and health status in northern and southern Nigeria. Drawing from their findings they concluded that in the light of low income of majority of the people especially in the north, the stewardship role of the government has to increase in terms of funding healthcare, if the health status of the populace is to improve. However, they are apt to note that without government being directly involved in the provision of healthcare services, an attempt should be made to subsidize the private sector and increase regulatory capacities (institutional quality) to improve the overall availability and accessibility of health services to the citizenry.

Damian and Chukwunonso (2014) investigated the effect of per capita income spending on child mortality in Nigeria using secondary data from 1980-2012. They examined the explanatory variables on the three dependent variables representing health outcome (under-five mortality, infant mortality and neonatal mortality rate) using multiple regression. The result shows that per capita health spending has no significant impact on infant mortality. However, the study finds a significant impact of per capita under-five mortality.

Boachie and Ramu (2016) examined the effect of public health expenditure on health status in Ghana using secondary data from the period between 1990-2012. The study employed ordinary least square (OLS) to ascertain the impact of per capita income on health status (infant mortality). The result shows that only public health expenditure and education significantly reduce infant mortality, while the per capita and female participation in the labour market both have negative but insignificant effects on infant mortality.

Oloo, Machuki, Momanyi, Ogwangi and Ochieng (2013) and Hakooma and Seshamani (2017) The findings of their study on bi-directional causality of human capital and economic growth in Kenya using the Ordinary Least Square Method and Zambia using the Error Correlation Model, respectively, revealed a positive and strong relationship between health expenditure and economic growth in both countries. Ogunbenle, Olawumi, and Obasuyi (2013) examined the relationship between life expectancy, public health spending, and economic growth in Nigeria using a vector autoregressive (VAR) model and discovered that there was a relationship between public health spending and economic growth.

Ibukun and Osinubi (2020) looked at the relationship between environmental quality, economic growth, and health spending in 47 African countries and discovered that economic growth has a positive and inelastic effect on health spending. Anowor, Ichoku, and Onodugo (2020) used GDP capital to investigate

the relationship between health financing and economic growth performance. Their research found that private and public health-care spending have a positive effect on economic performance, with a long-run correlation between health-care spending and output per capita in the ECOWAS region.

Olayiwola and Olusanya (2021) investigated the relationship between health financing and Nigerian economic growth and found that domestic private health expenditure has a significant positive growth effect on Nigerian economic growth. Aboubacar and Xu (2017) used the system general method of moments (GMM) technique to assess the impact of health spending on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa and discovered that health spending has a significant impact on the region's economic growth. Ojo and Ojo (2022) discovered that government expenditure on education and health had a positive and significant impact on economic growth in their study on health expenditure, education, and economic growth in Nigeria using the error correlation model (ECM) as an estimating approach

Finally, Awogbemi (2022) examined the impact of health expenditure on Nigeria's economic growth using Error Correction Model Estimates (ECME). The empirical results using the Error Correction Model Estimates does not found support for increasing health expenditure as it negatively affect economic growth of Nigeria both in the short-run and the long-run. He concluded that though government expenditure on health is very vital, emphasis must be placed on capital expenditure to a reasonable extent. Therefore, Nigerian government should intensify efforts towards increasing the Abuja declarations of allocating at least 13-15 percent of annual budget to the health sector for effect funding as well as focus more on health outcomes and its impacts on economic growth in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Theoretical Framework

An endogenous model of economic growth appears to be the most suitable theoretical framework for this study. Endogenous growth theory describe economic growth which is generated by factors within the production process such as economies of scale, increasing return or induced technological changes, government policies, political stability, market distortions, human capital etc., can significantly affect economic growth. The framework of this study assumes a standard neoclassical production function which premise on changes in quantities of factors of production account for growth. The neo-classical model is based on the Cobb-Douglas production function and is given as:

$$Y = f(A_t, K_t, L_t) \tag{1}$$

The neoclassical growth theory states that the changes in quantities of factor inputs in production (capital and labour) account for growth of output (Solow 1957). Where: Y = Aggregate real output, K = Capital, L = Labour force, A = Level of technology and t = time dimension.

Model Specifications

This study will adapt the model of Olayiwola, Bakare-Aremu and Abiodun (2021) on public health expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. The specification by Olayiwola, Bakare-Aremu and Abiodun (2021) is presented as follows:

$$PHEX_t = (GDP_t, HSTGEX_t, POPT_t) \tag{2}$$

$$PHEX_t = \alpha + \beta_1 GDPPC_{t-1} + \beta_2 HSTGEX_{t-2} + \beta_3 POPT_{t-3} + \varepsilon \tag{3}$$

Where: RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product, PHEX_t = public health expenditure (the outcome or dependent variable); GDPPC_t = Gross Domestic Product per Capita; HSTGEX_t = Health expenditure share in total government expenditure; POPT = Population. while ε = Error term.

The current study will modify equation 2 to capture health expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. The log linear form of the current specification is presented thus:

Model

$$RGDP_t = f(DGGHE_t, DPHE_t, OOP_t) \tag{4}$$

Equation 4 is expressed more specifically as equation 5

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DGGHE_t + \beta_2 DPHE_t + \beta_3 OOP_t + U_t \tag{5}$$

(Apriori expectation $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$)

Where RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product, DGGHE = Domestic General Health Expenditure, DPHE = Domestic Private Health Expenditure and OOP = Out-of-pocket, U_t = Error Term, β_0 = Intercept, β_1 – β_3 = Coefficient of the independent variables and t is the time trend.

Sources of Data

Data for this study will be obtained from secondary sources, which include Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2021), Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Report and Statement of Accounts (various issues), Nigerian Economic and Financial Reviews, Securities and Exchange Commission Statistical Bulletin (various issues), internet, academic journals, textbooks, seminar papers and the Nigerian Stock Exchange journals.

Methods of Data Analysis

The method used to analyse the data for the log-log linear modeling specification that is superior and more effective, and give more favorable results than the linear modeling estimation includes Descriptive Statistics, Unit Root Test, Co-integration Test, Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) methodology, Diagnostic Statistics and Stability Test.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This paper commenced its empirical analysis by examining the characteristics of the series used in it. The descriptive statistics of the entire data series is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

STATSIATIC	RGDP	DGGHE	DPHE	OOP
Mean	10.77617	2.953677	3.981880	13.01388
Median	10.39839	2.885632	4.664490	12.65453
Maximum	14.93000	3.586016	5.942799	15.40276
Minimum	7.757940	1.791759	-0.604404	5.164786
Std. Dev.	2.035937	0.510089	1.989624	3.442867
Skewness	0.401601	-0.346042	-0.811524	-0.498128
Kurtosis	2.146087	1.789565	2.454850	1.749446
Jarque-Bera	2.405023	3.402233	5.130075	4.473721
Probability	0.300439	0.182480	0.076916	0.106793
Observations	39	39	39	39

Source: Author Regression Output from EViews 9

From the descriptive statistics presented in Table 1, the normality test uses the null hypothesis of normality against the alternative hypothesis of non-normality. It was observed from the table that the mean and median of the selected health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria (RGDP) Real Gross Domestic Product, (DGGHE) Domestic General Health Expenditure, (DPHE) Domestic Private Health Expenditure, (OOP) Out-of-pocket) a displayed a high level of consistency, as their values are within the range of minimum and maximum values of the series. All the series have good evidence of evenly spread.

The standard deviation statistics of RGDP, DGGHE, DPHE, and OOP are 2.035937, 0.510089, 1.989624 and 3.442867 respectively. This implies that Out-of-pocket (OOP) with the value of 3.442867 was the most volatile series while Domestic General Health Expenditure (DGGHE)) with the value 0.510089 was the least volatile. The skewness statistics shows that real gross domestic product (RGDP) was positively skewed.

Unit Root Test Results

Prior to the estimation of ECM, unit root test were conducted on the selected macroeconomic indicators (Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Domestic General Health Expenditure (DGGHE), Domestic Private Health Expenditure (DPHE), Out-of-pocket (OOP)), using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the Phillips-Perron (PP) test statistics to determine their stationarity status. Statistical theory requires that variables be stationary before application of standard econometric techniques. This was done in order to avoid spurious (misleading) results. The results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and the Phillips-Perron unit root test statistics are displayed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: The Augmented Dickey-Fuller and the Phillips-Perron Unit Root Test Results

Variable	ADF at Level	ADF at First Difference	PP at Level	PP at First Difference	Order of Integration
RGDP	0.146539 (0.9647)	-2.955480 (0.0495)	0.503708 (0.9845)	-2.983650 (0.0566)	I(1)
DGGHE	2.516507 (1.0000)	-4.667902 (0.0007)	4.558902 (1.0000)	-4.638783 (0.0007)	I(1)
DPHE	-1.403521 (0.5694)	-6.322756 (0.0000)	-1.111317 (0.7003)	-8.415031 (0.0000)	I(1)
OOP	-1.633243 (0.4554)	-6.852800 (0.0000)	-1.740760 (0.4027)	-6.764196 (0.0000)	I(1)
5%CV	-2.951125	-2.960411	-2.948404	-2.951125	

Source: Author’s compilation with information from stationarity test results

- Note: (i) Pro-value are reported in parenthesis.
 (ii) The Augmented Dickey-Fuller and the Phillips-Perron test statistics were compared to 5 per cent critical value (C.V).

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller and the Phillips-Perron test results which are displayed in Table above shows that all the selected variables (RGDP, DGGHE, DPHE and OOP) were all stationary at first difference I(1).

Cointegration Test Results

The next step after determining the order of integration of the selected health expenditure and macroeconomic variables was to examined the cointegration test statistics using the Johansen cointegration technique in order to establish the existence or otherwise of longrun relationship among the variables in the models starting with the null hypothesis that there are no cointegrating vector in the estimated models. The results of the Unrestricted Cointegration Rank tests for the models are presented in Tables below.

Table 3: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test result for the Model

Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Trace Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**	Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Max-Eigen Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**
None*	107.2338	69.81889	0.0000	None*	46.62560	33.87687	0.0009
At most 1*	60.60822	47.85613	0.0020	At most 1*	28.10088	27.58434	0.0429
At most 2*	32.50734	29.79707	0.0238	At most 2	19.72758	21.13162	0.0776
At most 3	2.680510	3.841466	0.1016	At most 3	2.680510	3.841466	0.1016

Source: Author’s compilation with information from cointegration rank test results.

- Note: (i) No. CE(s) represents number of cointegrating equations.
 (ii) Both Trace and Max-Eigenvalue tests indicates 3 and 2 cointegrating equations at the 0.05 level respectively.
 (iii) * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level
 (iv) ** Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis(1999) p-values

The results of the unrestricted cointegration rank test for the pooled model on ADI which are displayed in Table, showed that there exists at least three (3) and two (2) cointegrating relationship in the model as both the Trace and Max-Eigen statistics rejected the null against the alternative at 5 per cent level of significance which shows that there is a unique longrun relationship between Real Gross Domestic

Product (RGDP), Domestic General Health Expenditure (DGGHE), Domestic Private Health Expenditure (DPHE) and Out-of-pocket (OOP)

Error Correction Representation (Short-run) Results for Health Expenditure and political Economic Growth in Nigeria

The error correction mechanism (ECM) in all the estimated models (Health Expenditure and political Economic Growth model) were examined to show the speed of adjustment at which any disequilibrium experienced in the system at the short run was adjusted back to long run equilibrium. The results of the error correction representation for the impact of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria are reported in Table below:

Error Correction Representation (Short-Run) Results for Health Expenditure and political Economic Growth in Nigeria

The results of the error correction representation of the impact of Health Expenditure on political Economic Growth in Nigeria (1986-2022) are reported in Table below.

Table 4: Error Correction Representation (Short Run) Results for the Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	21.34615	2.238801	9.534634	0.0000
D(DGGHE)	0.620030	0.202430	3.062935	0.0000
D(DPHE)	-0.381057	0.261353	-1.458066	0.9568
D(OOP)	0.217365	0.102621	2.118134	0.0243
ECM(-1)	-0.626902	0.142954	-4.385341	0.0001
R-squared	0.688653	Mean dependent var		40208.00
Adjusted R-squared	0.529455	S.D. dependent var		20836.83
S.E. of regression	7528.566	Akaike info criterion		20.84560
Sum squared resid	1.64E+09	Schwarz criterion		21.11223
Log likelihood	-358.7980	Hannan-Quinn criter.		20.93764
F-statistic	46.28919	Durbin-Watson stat		1.833656
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Author's compilation with information from Regression Output.

The short run error correction results presented in Table 4.5a showed that the entire explanatory variables of the estimation met their expected signs for the model except Domestic Private Health Expenditure (DPHE) with a negative sign. The empirical results also revealed that Domestic General Health Expenditure (DGGHE) has direct and significant impact on the real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria for the sample period. This means that 1 per cent increase in Domestic General Health Expenditure raised real gross domestic product in Nigeria by 62.0 per cent. This result is consistent with previous empirical studies of Afolabi (2020).

The results also revealed that Domestic General Health Expenditure (DGGHE) of the Nigerian economy had inverse and significant relationship with the real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. Thus, 1 per cent change in all share index of the Nigerian capital market reduced real gross domestic product in Nigeria by 38.1 per cent. This is consistent with the work of Esieba (2021).

The empirical evidence from the short run results also revealed that Out-of-pocket (OOP) had positive and significant impact on the real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria from 1986 to 2021. This implies that one per cent increase in foreign direct investment raised real gross domestic product in Nigeria by 21.7 per cent. This result is consistent with previous empirical studies of Muyiwa (2019)

The error correction mechanism (ECM) which is -0.626902 is statistically significant and has the appropriate negative sign. It suggests however, that there is a high adjustment process in the activities of Health Expenditure and the real gross domestic product in Nigeria. It is also a confirmation that indeed

Real Gross Domestic Product, Domestic General Health Expenditure, Domestic Private Health Expenditure and Out-of-pocket are cointegrated.

Finally, the coefficient of determination R^2 of 68.9 per cent indicates that the total variation on real gross domestic product in Nigeria is jointly explained by Domestic General Health Expenditure, Domestic Private Health Expenditure and Out-of-pocket in Nigerian. The Akaike information criterion, Schwarz criterion and Hannan-Quinn criterion showed that the model is correctly specified. F statistic measuring the joint significant of all regressors in the model is statistically significant at the 5 per cent level. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.833656 approximately 2 revealed the absence of autocorrelation among the explanatory variables.

Diagnostic Test Results

To confirm the robustness of the models estimated for the impact of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria, diagnostic tests were performed as shown in Tables below.

Diagnostic Test Results for Health Expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product Model

To confirm the robustness of the model on health expenditure t and real gross domestic product in Nigeria, four econometric diagnostic tests were performed to reaffirm the key regression statistics for the model, starting with the Normality test, Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test, Harveytest of Heteroskedasticity and Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test of Heteroskedasticity. The results are presented in Table below and Test for Normality chart in figure 4.6a respectively.

Table 5: Diagnostic Tests Results for Health Expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	
F-statistic = 41.29046	Prob. F(2,30) = 0.0000
Obs*R-squared = 22.76732	Prob. Chi-Square(2) = 0.0000
Heteroskedasticity Test: Harvey	
F-statistic = 8.862981	Prob. F(4,31) = 0.0001
Obs*R-squared = 19.20590	Prob. Chi-Square(4) = 0.0007
Scaled explained SS = 12.49785	Prob. Chi-Square(4) = 0.0140
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	
F-statistic = 3.302661	Prob. F(4,31) = 0.0294
Obs*R-squared = 10.29179	Prob. Chi-Square(4) = 0.0358
Scaled explained SS = 4.663855	Prob. Chi-Square(4) = 0.3236

Source: Author Regression Output from EViews 9

Figure1: Plot of Normality Test

The diagnostic tests results of Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test, Harvey’s test of Heteroskedasticity and Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test of Heteroskedasticity all revealed not only the robustness of the estimated equation but the desired properties of a well estimated econometric model.

The f-value of the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test (41.29046) indicated that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation is accepted ($p < 0.05$). Also, Harvey test of heteroskedasticity has a null hypothesis which states that homoscedasticity does not exist, that is, the variance of the error term is homoscedastic. Since the p-value of the statistics are less than the appropriate threshold ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity is hereby retained. Furthermore, the results of the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test of heteroskedasticity with f-value (3.302661) revealed that the null hypothesis which states that homoscedasticity does not exist is accepted since the p-value of the statistics are less than the appropriate threshold ($p < 0.05$).

Stability Test Results

The stability test results for the models on the impact of health expenditure on political economic growth in Nigeria are reported in the Figures below.

Stability Test Results for Health Expenditure and Economic Growth Model

Stability test was performed on health expenditure and economic growth model using cumulative sum (CUSUM) and cumulative sum of square (CUSUM Q) of recursive residuals as shown in Figures below. The existence of parameter instability is established if the cumulative sum of the residuals for health expenditure and economic growth model goes outside the area between the critical lines.

Figure 2: Cumulative Sum of Recursive Residuals

Figure 3: Cumulative Sum of Squares of Recursive Residuals

From Figure 2 and 3, it was observed that capital market and economic growth model at 5 per cent level of significance, CUSUM and CUSUM Q were both stable over time because the observed bound lied between the upper and lower limit. In conclusion, at 5 per cent critical value CUSUM and CUSUM Q both explain the stability of health expenditure and political economic growth in Nigeria during the estimated period.

CONCLUSION

The correlation between health expenditures and political economic growth is paramount in any economy. It is paramount to take cognizance of the fact that health expenditures strengthen the health system and contribute directly to the strengthening of the institutional infrastructure for health and the improvement of the health conditions of citizens. The effect of public health expenditure on economic growth is constrained by different external factors. The final effect of public health expenditure on economic growth is significantly positive, which is consistent with the research findings of Chang, Chang and Wang (2022)

The study has reached broadly consistent research conclusions with previous authors, revealing significant threshold effects of public health expenditure on political economic growth. Also, the positive correlation of health expenditures on growth reveals that the public give stronger attention to health expenditures, because health expenditures are not only limited to improving the living conditions of people, but also feed human and physical capital, which is an important component of production factors, and thus become determinants for economic growth.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the paper recommends thus:

- i. Public interest should be the overriding motive for government budgetary allocations especially in critical sectors like health in line with global standards. In this view, budgetary allocation of the various tiers of government in Nigeria for health sector should favourably compete with the WHO minimum Benchmark of 14USD per Capital for developing countries
- ii. While arresting the inadequacy of budgetary allocation to the health sector, the issue of effective management of the various health facilities should be seriously considered. Emphasis should be placed on good corporate management as this is crucial to the effective administration of the various health services and products to concerned Nigerians devoid of corruption, favouritism, selfish interest, nepotism and promotion of class interest.
- iii. Remuneration as well as Training Opportunities for health care providers should be made more regular and comprehensive in view of the changing world.
- iv. Government of different levels should monitor their Health Care Programmes to ensure that its benefits reach the grass root.

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